

COST, RETURNS, PROFITABILITY AND MARKETING OF TURMERIC IN SANGLI DISTRICT OF MAHARASHTRA, INDIA

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Abstract

The current study was designed to assess the input use, cost structure, and return on investment in the turmeric production of the Sangli district of Maharashtra, India. In the current study, 96 turmeric farmers were chosen from the study area to examine the input use, cost structure, and returns in turmeric growers' production and marketing in 2020-21. The current study was conducted in the Sangli district of Maharashtra. Cost-A was ₹ 184469.86 and Cost-B was ₹ 261977.78, for a total cost per hectare of ₹ 293333.28 for turmeric. The output-input ratio was 1.26, showing that the turmeric production is really profitable. Significant factors included the surrounding area, hired human labour, seed, fertilizer, machine labour, and family labour. The current study has been conducted for this reason.

Keywords: Turmeric, Cost, Returns, Profitability

Introduction

Turmeric got its name from the Middle English or Early Modern English words turmeryte or tarmarate. It could be of Latin origin, terra merita, which means "meritorious earth." Turmeric is a flowering plant in the ginger family Zingibaraceae with the botanical name *Curcuma longa*. The turmeric processing industry is responsible for the creation of thousands of job opportunities across the country. In terms of total turmeric production, Maharashtra came in second, followed by Tamil Nadu, Gujarat, and Orissa.

India has the greatest number of *Curcuma* species diversity, with around 40 to 45 species. Thailand has 30 to 40 species that are comparable. There are numerous wild *Curcuma* species in other tropical Asian countries. Recent research has also revealed that the taxonomy of *Curcuma longa* is problematic, with only specimens from South India identifying as *C. longa*. Other species and cultivars' phylogeny, relationships, intraspecific and interspecific variation, and even identity in other parts of the world must still be established and validated. Several species sold as "turmeric" in other parts of Asia have been shown to belong to several physically similar taxa with overlapping local names. Turmeric has been used for centuries in Asia and is an important part of Ayurveda, Siddha medicine, traditional Chinese medicine, Unani, and Austronesian animistic rituals. It was first used as a dye, and then for its supposed medicinal properties.

Turmeric production in world, India and Maharashtra is 9389.55 MT, 1330.93 MT and 367.99 MT respectively in 2020-21. (Source: indiastat.com)

In India area under turmeric is 2.91 lakh ha with a productivity of 3656 kg/ha during 2020-21. (Source: Third Advance estimates, agricoop.nic.in)

In Maharashtra area and productivity of turmeric is 10263 ha and 3.59 MT/ha respectively in 2020-21. (Source: indiastat.com)

In Sangli district area under turmeric is 1500 ha, whereas production and productivity is 13000 tonnes and 8.6 tonnes/ha, respectively in 2020-21. (Source: www.ijcmas.com)

Objectives

1. To estimate per hectare cost, return and profitability of turmeric.

Materials and Methods

For the 2020-21 study year, data on associated parts of the study were collected by a survey method from sample cultivars. The data was collected using a personal interview method. The survey approach

was used to collect data on relevant factors such as input utilization, and cost of different inputs, yield obtained, turmeric farming, and marketing from sample growers. Farmers were interviewed in person at their farms and residences, as well as in some cases in public venues in the village. The data was gathered according to a study-specific, pre-tested time table.

Statistical Tools applied: Frequency, Percentage. Average

Results and Discussion**1. Physical inputs and outputs in turmeric production.**

Per hectare physical inputs and outputs of turmeric production were calculated and presented in table 1. It was observed that, the use of hired human labour was 68.54, family human labour was 86.64 man days and use of bullock labour was 0.64 pair days in turmeric farm. On the contrary, use of machine labour was 8.16 hours/ha. The use of rhizome was 24.56 qt/ha in turmeric farm. In regard to manure, the quantity of 20.16 quintals/ha was used in turmeric farm. Use of nitrogen, phosphorous and potash was 53.96, 53.95 and 89.48 kg/ha, respectively in turmeric farm. Use of plant protection was in that fungicides 5.48 and insecticides 3.57 litre. Use of irrigation was 20.16 no. of irrigation in turmeric farm. It was also observed that, production from fresh fingers of turmeric was 42.5 quintals/ha and from fresh mother sets was 6.22 quintals/ha.

2. Per hectare cost of cultivation of turmeric production

Per hectare cost of cultivation of turmeric were calculated and mentioned in table 2. The result revealed that, the per hectare cost of cultivation was ₹ 293333.28 in which Cost-A consist ₹ 184469.86 i.e. 62.89 per cent, Cost-B, ₹ 261977.78 i.e. 89.31 per cent and Cost-C is ₹ 294815.37 i.e. 100 per cent respectively. Expenditure on hired human labour was ₹ 22662.89 i.e. 7.73 per cent. Next item of expenditure is machine labour i.e. ₹ 8956.28 (3.05 per cent), Bullock labour accounted, ₹ 350.81 (0.12 per cent), rhizome ₹ 120852 (41.20 per cent), manure ₹ 11728.83 (4.00 per cent), Nitrogen ₹ 388.52 (0.13 per cent), Phosphorous ₹ 390.6 (0.13 per cent), Potash ₹ 1789.61 (0.61 per cent), Plant protection ₹ 756.96 (0.26 per cent), Land revenue ₹ 60.34 (0.02 per cent), Incidental charges ₹ 355.54 (0.12 per cent), Interest on working capital ₹ 10182.85 (2.05 per cent), Depreciation on capital assets ₹ 5994.64 (3.47 per cent), Rental value of land ₹ 61595.07 (21.00 per cent), Interest on fixed capital ₹ 15912.85 (5.42 per cent) and Family human labour ₹ 31355.5 (10.69 per cent) respectively.

Table 1: Per hectare of physical input and output in turmeric production (Unit/ha)

Sr. No.	Particulars	Unit	Average
	INPUT		
1.	Hired human labour	man days	
	Male		45.45
	Female		23.09
2.	Family human labour	man days	
	Male		68.09
	Female		18.55
3.	Bullock labour	pair days	0.64
4.	Machine labour	hours	8.16
5.	Rhizomes	qt.	24.56
6.	Manures	qt.	20.16
7.	Fertilizer		
	Urea	kg	53.96
	SSP	kg	53.95
	MOP	kg	89.48
8.	Plant Protection		
	Fungicides	kg/lit	5.48
	Insecticides	kg/lit	3.57
9.	OUTPUT		
	Fresh fingers	qt.	42.5
	Fresh Mother sets	qt.	6.22

Table 2: Per hectare cost of cultivation of turmeric crop (₹/ha)

Sr. No.	Particulars	Amount (₹)	Per cent
1.	Hired human labour	22662.89	7.73
2.	Machine labour	8956.28	3.05
3.	Bullock labour	350.81	0.12
4.	Rhizome	120852	41.20
5.	Manure	11728.83	4.00
6.	Fertilizer		
	Urea	388.52	0.13
	SSP	390.6	0.13
	MOP	1789.61	0.61
7.	Plant protection	756.96	0.26
8.	Land revenue	60.34	0.02
9.	Incidental charges	355.54	0.12
10.	Interest on working capital @ 6%	10182.85	2.05
11.	Depreciation on capital assets	5994.64	3.47
12.	Cost-A (Σ 1 to11)	184469.86	62.89
13.	Rental value of land	61595.0767	21.00
14.	Interest on fixed capital @ 11%	15912.85	5.42
15.	Cost-B (Σ 12 to14)	261977.78	89.31
16.	Family human labour	31355.5	10.69
17.	Cost-C (Σ 15 to16)	293333.28	100

3. Per hectare Profitability of turmeric production (₹/ha)

Per hectare profitability in turmeric production was calculated and mentioned in table 3. The results revealed that, per hectare gross return was found to be ₹ 369932.5 in turmeric farm as given in table 4.6. It was clear that, farm business income, family labour income and net profit/ha were ₹ 185462.64, ₹ 107954.72 and ₹ 76599.21 respectively. It was clear that, output-input ratio was 1.26. Turmeric crop was profitable enterprise. Per quintal cost of production of turmeric was ₹ 6022.03.

Table 3: Per hectare profitability of turmeric production

Sr. No.	Particulars	Physical unit	Physical quantity	Amount (₹)
1.	Return from fresh fingers	Qt.	42.5	328213.22
2.	Return from fresh mother sets	Qt.	6.22	41719.31
3.	Gross return (Σ 1 to 2)	–		369932.5
4.	Cost-A	–		184469.86
5.	Cost-B	–		261977.78
6.	Cost-C	–		293333.28
7.	Farm business income (Gross return minus Cost-A)	–		185462.64
8.	Family labour income (Gross return minus Cost –B)	–		107954.72
9.	Net Profit (Gross return minus Cost-C)	–		76599.21
10.	Benefit- Cost ratio (Gross return divided by Cost-C)	–		1.26
11.	Per quintal cost of production (Cost-C minus by produce value divided by main produce quantity)	–		6022.03

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